

1 **Oxidation of imidacloprid insecticide through PMS activation using**
2 **CuFe₂O₄ nanoparticles: role of process parameters and surface**
3 **modifications**

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25 **Abstract**

26

27 The contamination of water bodies by synthetic organic compounds coupled with
28 climate change and the growing demand for water supply calls for new approaches to
29 water management and treatment. To tackle the decontamination issue, the activation of
30 peroximonosulfate (PMS) using copper magnetic ferrite (CuMF) nanoparticles prepared
31 under distinct synthesis conditions was assessed to oxidize imidacloprid (IMD)
32 insecticide. After optimization of some operational variables, such as CuMF load (62.5-
33 250 mg L⁻¹), PMS concentration (250-1000 μmol L⁻¹), and solution pH (3-10), IMD
34 was completely oxidized in 2 h without interferences from leached metal ions. Such
35 performance was also achieved when using tap water but was inhibited by a simulated
36 municipal wastewater due to scavenging effects promoted by inorganic and organic
37 species. Although there was evidence of the presence of sulfate radicals and singlet
38 oxygen oxidizing species, only four intermediate compounds were detected by liquid
39 chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry analysis, mainly due to hydroxyl
40 addition reactions. Concerning the changes in surface properties of CuMF after use, no
41 morphological or structural changes were observed except a small increase in the charge
42 transfer resistance. Based on the changes of terminal surface groups, PMS activation
43 occurred on Fe sites.

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45

46 **Keywords:** Advanced oxidation process; heterogeneous catalysis; emerging
47 contaminants; hydroxyl radicals; *in situ* chemical activation

48

49 **Abbreviations**

50

51 AsP – As-prepared samples without *in situ* chemical activation using an oxidizer

52 Cpt 400 – CuFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite prepared by the co-precipitation method and

53 thermally treated at 400 °C for 1 h

54 Cpt 700 – CuFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite prepared by the co-precipitation method and

55 thermally treated at 700 °C for 1 h

56 CuMF: copper magnetic ferrite

57 DMPO - 5,5-dimethyl-1-pyrroline *N*-oxide

58 EI - Electrochemical impedance

59 FTIR – Fourier transform infrared

60 HRTEM – high-resolution transmission electron microscopy

61 HO• – hydroxyl radical

62 HPLC – high-performance liquid chromatography

63 ICP-OES – Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry

64 IMD – Imidacloprid insecticide

65 IMD fraction – $100 \times [\text{IMD}]_t / [\text{IMD}]_0$: [IMD] concentration at a specific time (*t*) and *t* = 0

66 MS/MS – tandem mass spectrometry

67 ¹O₂ – singlet oxygen

68 PMS – peroxymonosulfate

69 SO₄^{•-} – sulfate radical

70 SG 400 – magnetic CuFe₂O₄ ferrite prepared by the sol-gel method and thermally

71 treated at 400 °C for 1 h

72 SG 700 – CuFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite prepared by the sol-gel method and thermally

73 treated at 700 °C for 1 h

- 74 UHPLC-QToF MS - ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography coupled to a time-
- 75 of-flight mass analyzer
- 76 Us – Assayed samples for the *in situ* chemical activation of PMS to oxidize IMD
- 77 XRD – X-ray diffraction
- 78 XPS – X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy
- 79

80 1. Introduction

81

82 The serious implications of climate change and water pollution are pressing and
83 threaten our environment with potential impacts on human health and well-being
84 (Sangkham et al., 2023). The consequences of water pollution, especially persistent
85 organic pollutants (POPs) (Najam and Alam, 2023) are far-reaching and may include
86 damage to ecosystems resulting in poor water quality making it toxic to humans (Khan
87 et al., 2023; Li et al., 2023) with consequences for the economy and lifestyle (Beghetto
88 et al., 2023; Ercin and Hoekstra, 2016; Pandey et al., 2023).

89 To address this problem, treatment methods that involve new engineered
90 materials (Ahmad et al., 2023; Dai et al., 2023; Du et al., 2023; Nath et al., 2023) must
91 be developed. For this purpose, advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) are a set of
92 techniques that have gained significant attention due to their potential to deal with
93 environmental challenges, such as wastewater treatment (Gonçalves et al., 2023). The
94 wide applicability of AOPs lies on their capacity to produce high oxidizing radical
95 species, such as hydroxyl (HO^\bullet) and sulfate ($\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$), mainly through activation of
96 peroxy-derived chemicals, such as hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), peroxydisulfate (PDS,
97 $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$), and peroxymonosulfate (PMS, HSO_5^-) (Liu et al., 2023; Wu and Kim, 2022).
98 As these oxidation species are highly reactive, side reactions with inorganic (halides and
99 oxyanions) and organic (humic acids) compounds may lead to low efficiencies toward
100 the oxidation of target pollutants. Alternatively, non-radical species represented by
101 singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$) and high-valent metal (Yan et al., 2023) or even direct reaction of
102 PDS and PMS could be an option for high selectivity at the cost of low pollutant
103 oxidation kinetics (Hayat et al., 2020; Yu et al., 2021). Electrophilic addition reactions
104 to unsaturated moieties are the pathways chosen for non-radical species, whereas

105 electron transfer, hydrogen atom abstraction, or electrophilic addition (Gligorovski et
106 al., 2015) are the main degradation routes for radical species. Moreover, effective *in situ*
107 generation of radical and non-radical species also depends on the choice of adequate
108 methods and materials. Among the latter, oxides derived from transition metals are of
109 great interest (Zeng et al., 2023).

110 Magnetic ferrites, specifically spinel ferrites (MFe_2O_4 where $M=Zn, Ni, Co, Cu,$
111 Mn), are widely used in advanced oxidation processes (Sun et al., 2022) due to their
112 ease reusability and valence variability resulting in different electronic, structural, and
113 surface properties that boost the oxidation of organic compounds (Du et al., 2023).
114 Among ferrites, $CuFe_2O_4$ is an option due to the variable pathways of activation of PDS
115 and PMS that involve the formation of radical (mainly HO^\bullet and $SO_4^{\bullet-}$) and non-radical
116 ($Cu(III) / Cu(II) / Cu(I)$ and 1O_2) species (Ding et al., 2022). Wang et al., (2020)
117 showed that traces of $Cu(II)$ ions ($10 \mu mol L^{-1}$ using $400 \mu mol L^{-1}$ PMS at pH 8) can
118 lead to complete oxidation of 2,4-dichlorophenol and 1,4-dioxane compounds in
119 carefully pH controlled solutions using borate buffer. Cai et al., (2020) also observed
120 fast and complete oxidation of bisphenol A after 15 min (*ca.* $10 \mu mol L^{-1}$ $Cu(II)$ and 1
121 $mmol L^{-1}$ PMS in a phosphate buffered solution at pH 7) under formation of
122 $Cu(I)/Cu(III)$ species along with HO^\bullet , $SO_4^{\bullet-}$, and $O_2^{\bullet-}$ radicals. Feng et al., (2016) and
123 Zhang et al., (2013) reported PMS activation promoted by $Cu(II)/Fe(III)$ sites on the
124 $CuFe_2O_4$ solid, without contributions from aqueous $Cu(II)$ ions. Nevertheless,
125 uncertainties regarding the contribution of the solid catalyst and/or leached Cu ions still
126 exists including the activation of oxidants as well as surface changes after contact with
127 oxidants/pollutants.

128 Therefore, the aim of the present work is to synthesize, characterize, and use
129 $CuFe_2O_4$ magnetic ferrite ($CuMF$) nanoparticles for the *in situ* chemical activation of

130 PMS to oxidize imidacloprid (IMD) insecticide. The effect of different synthesis
131 procedures, heat treatments, CuMF load, PMS concentration, pH and use of borate
132 buffer was investigated. The pristine and assayed CuMF underwent a series of
133 characterizations to assess their morphology, crystalline structure, surface oxidation
134 state, and electrochemical parameters. These assessments were conducted using a
135 variety of techniques, including high-resolution transmission electron microscopy
136 (HRTEM), X-ray diffraction, Fourier transform infrared (FTIR), X-ray photoelectron
137 spectroscopy (XPS), and electrochemical measurements. To identify the primary
138 organic intermediates and working oxidants using a spin probe, ultra-high-performance
139 liquid chromatography coupled with quadrupole time-of-flight mass spectrometry
140 (UHPLC-QToF MS) was employed.

141

142 **2. Materials and methods**

143

144 *2.1 Chemical reagents*

145

146 Chemical reagents, including IMD (Imidacloprid, see chemical structure in Fig.
147 S1 – from Milenia Agrociencias S/A), $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (analytical
148 grade reagent, a.r., Acros Organics), NaOH (a.r., Panreac), Ethanol (absolute grade,
149 Sigma Aldrich), PVA (polyvinylalcohol - PVA, a.r., available as Mowiol[®] 18-88, Sigma
150 Aldrich), polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF, a.r., Sigma Aldrich), N-methyl pyrrolidone
151 (NMP, a.r. Sigma Aldrich), Ketjen Carbon Black 600 (KCB, Nouryon),
152 $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (a.r., Merck), K_2HPO_4 (a.r., Sigma Aldrich), H_2SO_4 (a.r., Merck),
153 $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (a.r., Synth), PMS (potassium peroxymonosulfate, a.r., available as
154 Oxone[®], Sigma Aldrich), KI (a.r., Synth), NaHCO_3 (a.r., Sigma Aldrich), DMPO (5,5-

155 dimethyl-1-pyrroline N-oxide, a.r., CaymanChem), isopropyl alcohol (IPA: 99.8%,
156 Panreac), t-butyl alcohol (TBA: 99.7%, Neon), furfuryl alcohol (FA: a.r., Sigma
157 Aldrich), L-histidine (L-H: a.r., Sigma Aldrich), HCOOH (a.r., J.T. Baker), CH₃OH
158 (HPLC grade, J.T. Baker) were used as received without prior treatment. All solutions
159 were prepared using deionized water (Millipore Milli-Q Direct-Q[®] 5 UV system, ρ
160 ≥ 18.2 M Ω cm).

161

162 *2.2 Synthesis of CuFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite (CuMF) nanoparticles.*

163

164 CuFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite nanoparticles were prepared by the sol-gel (SG) and
165 co-precipitation (Cpt) methods as reported in literature (Basak et al., 2021; Srinivasa
166 Rao et al., 2018) with some modifications. Briefly, in the first case, 1.0 g of polyvinyl
167 alcohol (PVA) was dissolved in 100 mL of water at 90 °C, then precursor salts,
168 Cu(NO₃)₂•3H₂O (0.001 mol) and Fe(NO₃)₃•9H₂O (0.002 mol) were added. After
169 complete drying, the resulting powder was collected and thermally treated in a muffle
170 furnace (400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h at a heating rate of 20 °C min⁻¹) under air conditions.
171 In the second case, the same amount of precursor salts was dissolved in absolute ethanol
172 under magnetic stirring, followed by the addition (32 mL) of a concentrated NaOH
173 solution (3 mol L⁻¹). The resulting mixture was kept under constant stirring for 30 min
174 under ambient conditions. Thereafter, the resulting solid material was then centrifuged
175 and washed several times with absolute ethanol and deionized water (until the washing
176 water reached pH 7) and finally dried at 60 °C for 24 h. After this step, the heat
177 treatment was carried out in a muffle furnace, as described above.

178

179 *2.3 CuMF characterization*

180 The surface morphology of the nanoparticles was analyzed using a TECNAI G²
181 F20 (FEI) Instrument high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM). X-
182 ray diffraction (XRD) experiments were performed using a D8 Advanced ECO
183 instrument (Bruker) in the reflection mode (Cu-K α_1 radiation of 1.54 Å, 40 kV, and 25
184 mA) at a scanning rate of 1° min⁻¹ from 5° to 90° (2 θ).

185 The surface elemental analysis of CuFe₂O₄ was performed by XPS using a
186 commercial spectrometer K-alpha XPS (Thermo Scientific). The Al K α line ($h\nu =$
187 1486.6 eV) was used as the ionization source and the pass energy of the analyzer was
188 set to 50 eV for the high-resolution spectra. Other parameters kept constant were spot
189 size (300 μm), step size (0.10 eV), dwell time (50 ms), and number of scans (10). The
190 inelastic background of the C 1s, O 1s, Cu 2p_{3/2} and Fe 2p_{3/2} high-resolution spectra was
191 subtracted using the Shirley method. The deconvolution of the experimental spectra was
192 performed using a Voigtian type function, with Gaussian (70%) and Lorentzian (30%)
193 combinations. The width at half height varied between 1.0 and 2.0 eV and the position
194 of the peaks was determined with an accuracy of ± 0.1 eV with respect to the
195 hydrocarbon peak located at 294.9 eV.

196 The surface functional groups were determined by using Fourier transform
197 infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy measurements. Samples were analyzed using the IR-
198 Prestige 21 spectrometer (Shimadzu) by the accumulation of 32 scans, operating from
199 4200 to 240 cm⁻¹. A small amount of nanoparticle powder (1 wt. %) was milled with
200 KBr, and a mixture was pressed into a pellet (10 mm in diameter) for analysis.

201 Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) was
202 carried out using a Thermo ICP OES iCAP 6000 (from Thermo Fischer Scientific). The
203 instrumental parameters optimized during analyses are described in Table S1.

204 Electrochemical impedance (EI) measurements (± 10 mV perturbation, 5 kHz –
205 0.5 mHz) and open circuit potential (OCP) measurements were performed in a solution
206 of 0.5 mol L^{-1} Na_2SO_4 under ambient conditions using a conventional three-electrode
207 cell with a Pt foil and an Ag/AgCl (3 mol L^{-1} KCl) as counter and reference electrode,
208 respectively. The working electrode was composed of a carbon paper substrate on
209 which a slurry containing a mixture of CuFe_2O_4 (75% *m/m*) was placed. The slurry was
210 prepared using 20% *m/m* KCB and 5% *m/m* PVDF, then deposited by drop coating and
211 left at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 12 h for solvent evaporation. The slurry was previously mashed in an
212 agate mortar and dispersed in $500 \text{ }\mu\text{L}$ of NMP. All measurements were carried out in the
213 dark.

214 Measurements were performed for the as-prepared CuMF samples (SG and Cpt)
215 and after 4 h of use. For this purpose, the catalyst samples were collected, filtered,
216 washed several times with deionized water, and dried under vacuum in a desiccator for
217 at least 12 h.

218

219 *2.4 IMD oxidation and analysis of treated solutions*

220 *In situ* chemical activation of PMS using CuMF for the oxidation of IMD (50
221 mg L^{-1}) was carried out in a water jacket glass vessel (150 mL) under magnetic stirring
222 in the dark. First, 100 mL of a buffered solution (10 mmol L^{-1} of KH_2PO_4 at pH 7 or
223 $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ at pH 8, 9 and 10) was added to the reaction vessel followed by the solid
224 CuMF. Then, the system was left under constant stirring for adsorption during 2 h.
225 Immediately after that, a certain amount of solid PMS was also added to start the
226 oxidation reaction. The effect of different parameters such as the CuMF dosage (62.5,
227 125, and 250 mg L^{-1}), PMS concentration (250, 500, and $1000 \text{ }\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$), solution pH
228 (3, 7, 8, 9 and 10), synthesis method (SG and Cpt), and thermal treatment ($400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and

229 700 °C) were studied. The solution pH was continuously monitored and manually
230 adjusted by adding concentrated/diluted H₂SO₄ or NaOH solutions. Other operational
231 variables, such as the treatment time, solution temperature, and stirring were kept
232 constant at 240 min, 25 °C, and 600 rpm, respectively. The samples were analyzed after
233 being collected from the reaction mixture at predetermined time intervals, filtered
234 through a 0.22 μm cellulose acetate cartridge, and quenched with excess Na₂S₂O₃ (1.0
235 mol L⁻¹), except when the residual oxidant was quantified. A recycling test (5
236 consecutive degradation experiments) was also carried out after optimization of the
237 above conditions. For this purpose, after each run, the CuMF catalyst was recovered by
238 vacuum filtration, washed thoroughly with deionized water, and dried under vacuum
239 prior to further use.

240 After the initial optimization using ultrapure water, tests were conducted on tap
241 water and a simulated municipal effluent wastewater (SMWW) to evaluate the impact
242 of typical inorganic and organic interferences in real-world scenarios. The
243 characterization and composition of these water matrices can be found in Table S2, S3,
244 and Text S1.

245 The evolution of IMD concentration was monitored by high performance liquid
246 chromatography (HPLC, Shimadzu 20A) at 270 nm using a core-shell C-18 reversed-
247 phase column as the stationary phase (150 mm × 4.6 mm i.d., 5 μm particle size, 100 Å
248 pore size, from Phenomenex[®]). A mixture of aqueous 0.1% (V/V) formic acid (eluent A)
249 and methanol (eluent B) was used as the mobile phase in a gradient elution mode (from
250 20% to 90% of B in 8 min and then, back to 20% after 2 min this condition was
251 maintained for 2 min before further analyses). The flow rate, injection volume, and
252 temperature of the column were kept fixed at 1.0 mL min⁻¹, 25 μL, and 24 °C,
253 respectively.

254 Ultra-high performance liquid chromatography coupled to a time-of-flight mass
255 analyzer (UHPLC-QToF MS) was used under optimized conditions to analyze
256 intermediates formed during the IMD oxidation process, according to a methodology
257 described in Text S2 and Table S4. The chromatographic procedures to determine
258 carboxylic acids and inorganic ions can be found in Text S3.

259 The amount of residual oxidant was determined using the spectrophotometric
260 method adapted from the work of Liang et al., (2008). Briefly, 2.0 mL of a 0.6 mol L⁻¹
261 KI and 0.06 mol L⁻¹ NaHCO₃ solution were added to 1.0 mL of previously filtered
262 sample. The resulting solutions were shaken by hand and allowed to stand for 15 min
263 before analysis on a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1800). The spectra were
264 obtained in the range of 200 to 400 nm and the analysis was performed at a wavelength
265 of 352 nm.

266 The main working oxidant species were assessed by *i*) UHPLC-QToF MS
267 analyses using a DMPO solution as spin probe (see Text S4 for details), *ii*) scavenging
268 experiments using isopropyl alcohol, t-butyl alcohol, furfuryl alcohol, and L-histidine at
269 0.1 mol L⁻¹, and *iii*) measurement of dissolved oxygen to account for the produced ¹O₂
270 species.

271

272 **3. Results and discussion**

273

274 *3.1 Characterization of the as-prepared CuFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite (CuMF)*

275 Fig. 1 shows transmission electron micrographs of the as-prepared CuMF
276 material synthesized by the SG and Cpt methods. All synthesized nanoparticles
277 exhibited a globular structure with many agglomerates. The mean particle size of the
278 samples heat treated at 700 °C exhibited a smooth distribution (refer to the histogram in

279 Fig. S2) with larger sizes compared to the condition at 400 °C, as shown in Table S5.
280 The estimated lattice fringe spacing of the HRTEM micrographs of Fig. S3 was 2.5 Å
281 (SG 400, Cpt 400, and Cpt 700 samples) and 2.6 Å (SG 700), corresponding to the
282 diffraction planes (113) and (013) of CuMF, respectively.

283 XRD measurements of the as-prepared (AsP) magnetic material using the SG
284 and Cpt synthesis procedure and thermally treated at 400 °C and 700 °C for 1 h can be
285 seen in Fig. S4. The SG 400, SG 700, and Cpt 400 samples exhibited diffraction peaks
286 that coincide with the tetragonal (ICSD 98-001-6666) and cubic (ICSD 98-018-5895)
287 phases, while the Cpt 700 samples exhibited only well-defined peaks attributed to the
288 cubic phase. Additional diffraction peaks at *ca.* 33° and 39° were not identified and
289 might be related to non-stoichiometric CuFe₂O₄ oxides.

290 The FTIR spectra of the as-prepared samples were very similar, as can be seen in
291 Fig. S5. In general, the main observed bands were ascribed to *i*) a weak band around
292 3400 cm⁻¹ due to the stretching of the O-H bond with respect to surface terminations
293 because of exposure to the environment (and consequent adsorption of moisture) or, in
294 the case of sol-gel synthesis, to traces of PVA; *ii*) C=C stretching at *ca.* 1600 cm⁻¹
295 (more intense for the SG 400 sample), *iii*) C-H bending at 1380 cm⁻¹, exclusively for
296 the SG 400 sample due to traces of PVA, and *iv*) Fe-O and Cu-O bond vibration bands
297 between 570 cm⁻¹ and 400 cm⁻¹, respectively.

298 *Ex situ* XPS measurements were performed to identify the surface composition
299 and bonding states of AsP CuFe₂O₄ nanoparticles. First, the C 1s spectra (refer to Fig.
300 S6) were deconvoluted into four (400 °C) and three (700 °C) peaks related to
301 hydrocarbons (C-H) at 284.9 eV and oxygenated groups of alcohol/ether (C-O type at
302 286 eV), carbonyl groups (C=O at 288 eV, except for the SG 700 and Cpt 700 samples),
303 and ester and carboxyl (-O-C=O at 288.5 eV and 289.3 eV) (Powell, 1989), mainly due

304 to carbon contamination of the surface and synthesis conditions. Regarding the O 1s
305 spectra, shown in Fig. S7, the main components are related to O-Metal (O^{-2}) bonds at
306 about 530 eV, hydroxyl groups (HO-Metal) at 531 eV, O-C and O-C=O type bonds
307 attributed to surface contamination (adventitious carbon) at about 532 eV and 533 eV,
308 respectively, and adsorbed H_2O at 535 eV (Powell, 1989). The main difference between
309 the spectra is a higher contribution of the O-Metal bonding for samples thermally
310 treated at 700 °C due to elimination of traces of synthesis precursor (in accordance with
311 FTIR experiments), lower carbon content and higher crystallinity. The Cu $2p_{3/2}$ high-
312 resolution spectra were fitted using five peaks, two of them shake-up satellites (940.6
313 and 943.0 eV) as shown in Fig. S8. The main components are related to Cu_2O at 932.4
314 eV, found only for samples treated at 400 °C, the most intense peak at 933 eV assigned
315 to CuO species, and $Cu(OH)_2$ surface groups at 935.3 eV, in agreement with the O 1s
316 component at 529 eV (Powell, 1989). Finally, the Fe $2p_{3/2}$ spectra (refer to Fig. S9) were
317 deconvoluted into four peaks attributed to FeO at 709.6 eV, Fe_2O_3 at 710.8 eV (main
318 peak for samples heat treated at 400 °C), FeOOH at 712.2 eV, and a shake-up satellite at
319 713.6 eV (Powell, 1989). A strong increase in the reduced iron species (Fe(II)) after
320 heat treatment at 700 °C is evident, while a higher number of Fe(III) species at 400 °C is
321 consistent with the appearance of the Cu(I) oxidation state.

322

323 *3.2 Evaluation of the catalytic performance of $CuFe_2O_4$ by the in situ activation of* 324 *PMS: effect of operational variables and water matrices*

325 The influence of catalyst load, PMS concentration, pH, and presence or absence
326 of buffer was investigated during *in situ* chemical activation of PMS by $CuFe_2O_4$.

327 First, Fig. 2a shows the evolution of the relative IMD concentration of the SG
328 400 sample as a function of treatment time using $500 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of PMS and a buffered

329 solution at pH 8. As expected for a heterogeneous process, the increase of the catalyst
330 load (from 62.5 to 250 mg L⁻¹) led to a higher oxidation rate (from 1.9 ±0.3 to 7 ±1
331 ×10⁻² min⁻¹ - see the pseudo first-order kinetic constants on Table S6) of IMD and to an
332 increasing consumption rate of PMS (see Fig S10a). The sole use of PMS was unable to
333 produce significant levels of IMD oxidation as only 14% of PMS was consumed after 4
334 h of experiment compared to over 80% consumption in the presence of CuMF.
335 Therefore, for the remaining experiments, the catalyst load was kept at 125 mg L⁻¹.

336 With respect to the influence of the initial PMS concentration on the oxidation of
337 IMD (Fig. 2b), concentration values higher than 500 μmol L⁻¹ are sufficient to obtain
338 almost complete oxidation levels (>90%) of IMD after 2 h of experiment. A significant
339 increase in pseudo first-order kinetic constants (see Table S7) was also observed from
340 250 (1.1 ±0.1 ×10⁻² min⁻¹) to 1000 μmol L⁻¹ (7 ±2 ×10⁻² min⁻¹), despite similar levels
341 of PMS consumption (70% and 90% after 2 and 4 h of experiment – see Fig. S10b).
342 Once again, the sole use of CuMF nanoparticles was unable to oxidize IMD as no
343 additional removal of the organic compound was noticed after the adsorption time.
344 Based on these results, we conducted the next experiments using 500 μmol L⁻¹ of PMS.

345 To evaluate the possible effects of the distinct synthesis and thermal treatments
346 used to produce CuMF nanoparticles on the IMD oxidation by the *in situ* chemical
347 activation of PMS, all materials were assessed using 125 mg L⁻¹ of catalyst and 500
348 μmol L⁻¹ of PMS. As can be observed in Fig. 3a, no significant difference regarding
349 IMD oxidation levels (complete oxidation in less than 2 h) and rates (from 3.6 to 9.571
350 × 10⁻² min⁻¹ – see Table S8) were observed, despite the small variation of the PMS
351 consumption levels (highest consumption when using Cpt 400 and lowest for SG 400
352 nanoparticles – see Fig S11a) in the time range of 1 h to 3 h. To understand the similar
353 performances of the synthesized solids and to examine a possible contribution of

354 homogeneous processes, ICP-OES assays were carried out after the adsorption process
355 (just before oxidant addition) and after 6 h (2 h of adsorption and 4 h after PMS
356 addition) of reaction to determine Cu and Fe ions in samples of Fig. 3a. As Table S9
357 shows, both metal ions were detected in most of the samples which were analyzed.
358 Taking into account the possible effect that such metallic ion contamination may have
359 on PMS activation, as described in the work of Wang et al., (2020) for Cu(II) ions, new
360 experiments were conducted in the presence of distinct amounts of Cu(II) and Fe(III).
361 As can be observed in Fig. 3b, the sole use of Cu(II) (from 25 to 100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ – tolerable
362 limit is 1,300 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (Manne et al., 2022)) or Fe(III) (50 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ – tolerable limit is 300
363 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (Khatri et al., 2017)) ions only led to a marginal level of IMD oxidation (approx.
364 10% after 4 h of the experiment) with no PMS consumption (less than 5% - see Fig.
365 S11b). This shows that PMS activation takes place mainly through CuMF nanoparticles.

366 Considering the similar IMD oxidation rate values obtained for the prepared
367 solids, further experiments were performed to investigate the effect of solution pH using
368 the SG 400 samples. In all of the examined pH ranges, IMD molecule was not charged
369 ($\text{p}K_{\text{a}}$ values of IMD are 1.56 and 11.12 (Chamberlain et al., 1996)) and therefore, no
370 electrostatic interactions between IMD and PMS or IMD and CuMF are expected. As
371 can be seen in Fig. 4a, a slight alkaline (pH 8) to alkaline solutions led to the highest
372 oxidation rates (ranging from 3.6 to $1.2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ – see Table S10) and levels
373 (almost complete oxidation at pH 8 and 9 – see Fig S12a). At pH 10, a considerable
374 decrease in oxidation level was observed because of the formation of less reactive $^1\text{O}_2$
375 oxidant species (Eq. 1), as the pH of the solution is higher than the second $\text{p}K_{\text{a}}$ (9.4)
376 (Yuan et al., 2017) value of PMS. That behavior agrees with the obtained point of zero
377 charge (PZC) of CuMF, at *ca.* 8.4 (see results of the zeta potential measurements in Fig.
378 S13 that agrees with reported value (Dong et al., 2023)), since a large electrostatic

379 repulsion is expected between PMS and CuMF nanoparticles at pH values higher than
380 9. Neutral to acidic (pH 3 and using 10 mmol L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄) solutions led to no oxidation
381 of IMD (not shown).

382

384

385 Concerning the effect of buffer salt at pH 8, Fig. 4b shows a slight decrease in
386 the levels of IMD oxidation of approximately 100% and 85% IMD removal in 30 min in
387 the absence or presence of Na₂B₄O₇, respectively. The calculated rates were 7.2 to 3.6 ×
388 10⁻² min⁻¹ (refer to Table S11) in the absence and presence of Na₂B₄O₇ buffer,
389 respectively. This behavior was expected and has already been reported due to the
390 scavenging effect promoted by the buffer salt (Wan et al., 2022). However, it's worth
391 noting that there are some studies that have reported opposite findings (Chen et al.,
392 2021). Contrary to expectations, a steep increase was achieved in PMS consumption in
393 the absence of buffer (see Fig. S12b). As the IMD oxidation in both conditions was
394 similar and taking into account the side reactions between the buffer salt and reactive
395 oxygen species, a higher PMS consumption was expected in the presence of Na₂B₄O₇.
396 When the pH of the solution was not controlled (Fig. S12c), both IMD oxidation and
397 PMS consumption were not altered. Thus, the use of buffer is recommended since PMS-
398 induced pH alteration without a buffer salt seems to affect the IMD oxidation
399 performance.

400 The effect of distinct water matrices was investigated using tap water and a
401 SMWW. As shown in Fig. S14, IMD was completely oxidized after 3 h of experiment
402 when using tap water with PMS consumption over 90%. In comparison to the
403 experiments performed using ultrapure water (3.6 ± 0.1 × 10⁻² min⁻¹), the pseudo first-

404 order kinetic constants using tap water ($4 \pm 2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ for three experiments)
405 remained very close. That behavior was unexpected since the presence of interfering
406 inorganic species are known to scavenge radical species and then could lead to a
407 decrease in the oxidation rate of IMD. The observed high PMS consumption and/or
408 production of non-radical species ($^1\text{O}_2$ – see discussion below) played significant roles
409 in the findings. On the other hand, when using the simulated municipal effluent
410 wastewater (SMWW), no oxidation of IMD was observed, due to the interference of
411 significant amounts of organic and inorganic species.

412

413 3.3 IMD degradation byproducts and pathways

414 UHPLC-QToF MS measurements were carried out using the SG 400 samples in
415 the optimized experimental conditions, *i.e.*, 125 mg L^{-1} CuMF, $500 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PMS, and
416 buffered solution at pH 8 and $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. During the *in situ* chemical activation of PMS to
417 oxidize IMD, only four intermediate compounds were detected after 4 h treatment (see
418 Table S12 and Fig. S15a for the extracted ion chromatograms as a function of time).
419 Considering the MS/MS analyses of the main detected compounds (see Fig. S15b-f) and
420 the proposed fragmentation route (see Fig. S16), three degradation pathways can be
421 proposed (see Fig. 5) resulting from *i*) rupture of imidazolidine ring (see product P1), *ii*)
422 consecutive hydroxylation reactions on the imidazolidine ring (see P2 and P3), and *iii*)
423 loss of the imidazolidine ring (see P4). Silva et al., (2023) investigated the
424 photochemical activation of PMS by Co_3O_4 nanoparticles immobilized onto a glass
425 microfiber filter to oxidize IMD. This process not only resulted in a high rate of IMD
426 oxidation but also produced similar hydroxylated intermediate compounds, namely P1,
427 P2, and P3. The use of oxygen-doped graphitic carbon nitride to activate PMS under
428 visible irradiation or photocatalysis mediated by TiO_2 P25 was conducted by Tan et al.,

429 (2022) and Náfrádi et al., (2021), respectively, which also led to similar hydroxylated
430 byproducts (P1 and P2).

431

432 *3.4 Assessment of the main produced working oxidants*

433 To confirm the presence of HO• species in the reaction medium during PMS
434 activation by CuMF, DMPO was used as scavenger and its main byproducts resulting
435 from HO• addition reactions were analyzed through UHPLC-QToF MS measurements,
436 as detailed in the Text S4. No intermediates were formed in the SO₄•⁻ addition reactions
437 due to the low stability of DMPO-SO₄ [38]. The primary detected DMPO byproducts
438 are outlined in the total and extracted ion chromatograms shown in Fig. S17. The
439 compounds that were identified include DMPO/2OH, DMPO/OH, 2DMPO/O-3H,
440 2DMPO/-H, and 2DMPO/-3H. As shown in Table S13, these compounds are the result
441 of either addition reactions involving HO• or the abstraction of hydrogen (H)
442 (commonly promoted by SO₄•⁻ radicals). The MS/MS and the proposed fragmentation
443 route of the main reported DMPO intermediate species are depicted in Fig. S18 and
444 S19, respectively, which is consistent with previous reports.

445 Experiments using IPA, FA, and L-H as scavengers resulted in a complete
446 inhibition of IMD oxidation. This suggests the contribution of both radical and non-
447 radical species, specifically HO• (inhibition in the presence of IPA) and ¹O₂ (inhibition
448 in the presence of L-H and FA, despite controversy on the use of the latter as scavenger
449 (Wang et al., 2023)) as illustrated in Fig. S20. When TBA was used, a compound more
450 selective for HO• radicals (Liang and Su, 2009), IMD was completely oxidized. This
451 behavior is likely attributable to the presence of SO₄•⁻ radicals, despite the solution pH,
452 since electron spin resonance experiments led to inconclusive results.

453 Finally, the amount of dissolved oxygen increased considerably when PMS was
454 activated by CuMF nanoparticles (Fig. S21), compared to the buffered solution (under
455 blank conditions, either in the presence or absence of PMS). That behavior suggests the
456 production of $^1\text{O}_2$ and its subsequent deactivation to triplet oxygen ($^3\text{O}_2$) over time. As
457 reported in a previous paper (Broterson et al., 2024), the use of 9,10-anthracenediyl-
458 bis(methylene)dimalonic acid, which is a specific compound to react with $^1\text{O}_2$ (Entradas
459 et al., 2020), led to inconclusive results.

460

461 *3.5 Recycling test and post mortem changes of CuFe₂O₄*

462

463 The recycling tests were carried out using the SG 400 sample in the optimized
464 experimental conditions (125 mg L⁻¹ CuMF, 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, buffered solution at
465 pH 8 and 25 °C) during five consecutive experiments. As can be seen in Fig. S22,
466 complete IMD oxidation was achieved after 2 h with similar pseudo first-order kinetic
467 constants ($5.2 \times 10^{-2} \pm 0.9 \text{ min}^{-1}$). Clearly, no significant changes were observed in the
468 CuMF behavior during successive tests.

469 Morphological, structural, electrochemical, and surface chemical group changes
470 were assessed for CuMF nanoparticles after their use of PMS activation (*i.e.*, on
471 samples of Fig. 3a). As shown in Fig. S23, a slight decrease in particle size was
472 observed for the SG 400 and Cpt 400 samples (see also Table S5 for the mean particle
473 size); however, no morphological (TEM micrographs were not showed but were similar
474 to the as-prepared samples) or structural changes were observed in the XRD of the
475 CuMF nanoparticles (see Fig. S24 and Fig. S25). Indeed, after use (Us) some non-
476 indexed peaks in the as-prepared (AsP) samples were absent (see asterisks at 33° and
477 39° on Fig S24 for the SG samples) probably due to its dissolution. Concerning FTIR

478 analyses before and after use, no changes were observed with respect to AsP samples
479 (see Fig. S26 and Fig. S27). The PVA residues over the CuMF nanoparticles were still
480 present after their use, which might suggest a permanent blocking of the catalytic
481 surface without deleterious performance towards PMS activation.

482 To analyze the evolution of near-surface layer, XPS measurements were carried
483 out as shown in Fig. S28 to S31. To simplify the analysis and comparison among
484 samples the peak area percentage of the surface chemical states was grouped. For the O
485 1s spectra (see Fig. S32), the most intense signal was observed for the O-Metal bonding
486 in which a significant rise occurred for the Cpt 400 sample after use. The HO-metal
487 group exhibited variations, especially for the samples heat treated at 400 °C. In the case
488 of Fe 2p_{3/2} spectra (see Fig. 6) similar trends were observed for the SG and Cpt samples,
489 that is, an increase in FeO (Fe(II) species) and a decrease in Fe₂O₃ (Fe(III) species) for
490 samples thermally treated at 400 °C and the opposite effect for samples heat treated at
491 700 °C. Considering Cu 2p_{3/2} signals, the most noticeable changes after use were due to
492 the disappearance of Cu₂O (Cu(I) species) in samples (SG or Cpt) heat treated at 400 °C
493 and a subsequent increase in CuO (Cu(II) species) as well as in surface hydroxylation.
494 Considering these results, PMS activation was likely to occur over Fe sites after
495 oxidation of the remaining Cu(I) species, which is not in good agreement with what was
496 reported by Cai et al., (2023) who described both metal sites (Fe and Cu) as active. For
497 the C 1s, no important changes were observed for the rise of the C-N (see Fig. S28)
498 chemical group at 285.7 eV for the SG 400 sample after use. This behavior might
499 indicate surface adsorption of IMD or its byproducts, as the direct electron transfer from
500 the solid material seems not feasible. The latter can be better seen by the OCP
501 determination over time, and after the addition of PMS and IMD, as shown in Fig. 7a.
502 No electrode potential variation was observed upon the addition of IMD (similar

503 behavior was obtained for the remaining samples – data not shown). For the Cpt
 504 samples, a K 2p_{3/2} peak was observed due to contamination of PMS salt and/or synthesis
 505 salt precursors.

506 Electrochemical impedance measurements were also carried out to assess the
 507 evolution of the charge transfer resistance of AsP and Us samples, as shown in the
 508 Nyquist and Bode plots of Fig. S33 to S36. The best fits for the experimental data were
 509 achieved using the equivalent circuit found in the insets. This circuit was made up of
 510 five components related to the *i*) solution resistance (R_{sol}), *ii*) activated carbon support
 511 charge transfer resistance (R_C) in parallel with a constant phase element CPE_C , and *iii*)
 512 oxide charge transfer resistance ($R_{ferrite}$) in parallel with a $CPE_{ferrite}$. To get a better
 513 understanding of each sample performance, $R_{ferrite}$ values were plotted in Fig. 7b. As can
 514 be observed, $R_{ferrite}$ values for Us conditions were slightly higher, except for the SG 400
 515 with a two order of magnitude increase in $R_{ferrite}$. That behavior might indicate that
 516 electron transfer through the surface of the CuMF nanoparticles was not significantly
 517 affected by PMS or IMD and its byproducts.

518 In view of the results of PMS activation using CuMF nanoparticles, the
 519 following mechanism may take place without apparent influence of the homogeneous
 520 process due to dissolved Cu(II) and/or Fe(III) ions: *i*) Cu(I) species are irreversibly
 521 oxidized to Cu(II) species (Eq. 2) that seems to no longer reacts, *ii*) Fe(III) and Fe(II)
 522 activate PMS through oxidation (Eq. 3) or reduction (Eq. 4) reactions leading to $SO_4^{\bullet-}$
 523 or $SO_5^{\bullet-}$ species that can be further converted to HO^{\bullet} (Eq. 5) or 1O_2 (Eq. 6). The small
 524 increase observed in HO groups is probably due to reaction of metal surface sites with
 525 H_2O (Eq. 7) (Lyu et al., 2022).

526

533

534 **4. Conclusions**

535

536 CuFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite (CuMF) nanoparticles were successfully synthesized,
 537 characterized, and used for the imidacloprid (IMD) insecticide oxidation through
 538 activation of peroximonosulfate (PMS) oxidant. High oxidation rates and high levels of
 539 IMD were found after optimization of catalyst load (125 mg L^{-1}), PMS concentration
 540 ($500 \text{ } \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$), solution pH (8), and the use of a buffer. For the latter, pH monitoring
 541 and correction is desired, as the addition of PMS drops pH values resulting in
 542 deleterious effect on the oxidation performance of CuFe_2O_4 . For all investigated
 543 synthesis methods, metal ion leaching, particle size, and structure had no influence on
 544 IMD oxidation through PMS activation. The use of a simulated municipal wastewater
 545 led to a complete inhibition of IMD oxidation due to the scavenging effects promoted
 546 by inorganic and organic species. Such behavior was not observed when using tap
 547 water.

548 A low number of oxidation byproducts was detected as a result of the addition
 549 reaction of hydroxyl radicals. Furthermore, this study found that the primary oxidizing
 550 agents produced after activating PMS were a combination of radical (HO^\bullet and $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$)
 551 and non-radical ($^1\text{O}_2$) species.

552 No morphological or structural changes were observed on the surface of CuMF
553 after its use for PMS activation, except a slight increase in the charge transfer
554 resistance; however, a significant chemical modification of the surface chemical states
555 was evident, particularly on sites containing Fe, which emphasizes their specific
556 activation function on PMS activation.

557

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559

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570

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750

FIGURE CAPTIONS

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752

753 **Fig. 1** – Micrographs obtained from transmission electron microscopy (TEM) for the
754 CuFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite nanoparticles prepared by the Sol-gel (a and b) and Co-
755 precipitation (c and d) methods and thermally treated at 400 °C (a and c) and 700 °C (b
756 and d).

757

758 **Fig. 2** Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction) as a function of treatment time (t) of
759 the SG sample prepared at 400 °C using distinct **a)** loads of CuFe_2O_4 and **b)** PMS
760 concentration values (see inset for details) at a CuFe_2O_4 load of 125 mg L⁻¹.
761 **Conditions:** 500 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$, 100 mL of treating
762 solution with 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD at 25 °C. Error bars refer to two repetitions, except for the
763 oxidant consumption. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

764

765 **Fig. 3** Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction) as a function of treatment time (t)
766 using **a)** CuMF nanoparticles prepared and heat treated under different conditions and
767 **b)** distinct concentration values of Cu(II) and Fe(III) ions (see inset for further details).
768 **Conditions:** 125 mg L⁻¹ CuMF, 500 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$, 100
769 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. Error bars refer to two repetitions, except for the
770 oxidant consumption. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

771

772 **Fig. 4** Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction) as a function of treatment time (t)
773 using **a)** distinct pH values and **b)** in the presence (w/ = with) or absence (w/o =
774 without) of 10 mmol L⁻¹ $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ buffer solution (see inset). **Conditions:** 125 mg L⁻¹
775 CuFe_2O_4 (SG 400 sample), 500 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PMS, 10 mmol L⁻¹ $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ (KH_2PO_4 at pH

776 7), 100 mL of treating solution with 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD at 25 °C. Error bars refer to two
777 repetitions, except for the oxidant consumption. All experiments were carried out in the
778 dark.

779

780 **Fig. 5** Proposed degradation pathways of IMD using the CuFe₂O₄ SG 400 sample to the
781 *in situ* chemical activation of PMS. **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS,
782 pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇, 25 °C and 125 mg L⁻¹ of the CuMF SG 400 sample.

783

784 **Fig. 6** Comparison of peak areas for the surface bonding chemical states obtained from
785 the Fe 2p_{3/2} (**a** and **b**) and Cu 2p_{3/2} (**c** and **d**) spectra using the sol-gel (SG) and co-
786 precipitation (Cpt) samples (as-prepared - AsP - and after use - Us) that were thermally
787 treated at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h. See inset for details.

788

789 **Fig. 7 a)** Electrode potential (*vs.* Ag/AgCl/KCl 3 mol L⁻¹) as a function of time for the
790 CuMF synthesized by the sol-gel (SG) method and thermally treated at 400 °C. A 0.5
791 mol L⁻¹ Na₂SO₄ (corrected to pH 8) solution at ambient conditions was used. The
792 arrows indicate the moment (after 1 h) when PMS and IMD were added into solution
793 and **b)** oxide charge transfer resistance (R_{ferrite}) for the as-prepared (AsP) and after use
794 (Us) samples of the CuMF. The exposed area was close to 1 cm² and error bars refer to
795 three repetitions.